

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
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Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100, г.
Бухара, ул. Гиждуванская, 23.

Телефон (99865) 223-00-50

Факс (99866) 223-00-50

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e-mail baymuradovravshan@gmail.com

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EVALUATION OF LIVER DYSFUNCTION IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES**Makhmudova M.R., Baratova M.S.**

Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sino, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Resume. The study presents the clinical data of 139 patients with arterial hypertension (AH) and ischemic heart disease (IHD). The cardiovascular system parameters and blood biomarkers were analyzed. According to the WHO, cardiovascular diseases cause 17.5 million deaths annually, accounting for one-third of global mortality. The prevalence of hypertension among adults ranges from 30% to 45%. AH and IHD are present in more than 50% and 34% of patients, respectively, contributing to the development of micro- and macrovascular diseases. Data indicate that the risk of cardiovascular complications is four times higher in patients with concomitant diabetes mellitus and hypertension.

Keywords: cardiovascular remodeling, arterial hypertension, IHD, heart failure, natriuretic peptide, glucose, cholesterol.

ЮРАК-ҚОН ТОМИР КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИДА ЖИГАР ДИСФУНКЦИЯСИНИ БАҲОЛАШ**Махмудова М.Р., Баратова М.С.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. Тадқиқотда артериал гипертензия (АГ) ва юрак ишемик касаллиги (ЮИК) бўлган 139 беморнинг клиник маълумотлари келтирилган. Юрак-қон томир тизими параметрлари ва қон биомаркерлари таҳлил қилинди. ЖССТ маълумотларига кўра, юрак-қон томир касалликлари ҳар йили 17,5 миллион ўлимга олиб келади, бу глобал ўлимнинг учдан бир қисмини ташкил қилади. Катталар орасида гипертензия тарқалиши 30% дан 45% гача. АГ ва ЮИК беморларнинг 50% ва 34% дан кўпрогида мавжуд бўлиб, микро ва макроваскуляр касалликларнинг ривожланишига ҳисса қўшади. Маълумотлар шуни кўрсатадики, қандли диабет ва гипертония билан оғриган беморларда юрак-қон томир асоратлари хавфи тўрт барабар юқори.

Калит сўзлар: артериал гипертензия, ЮИК, юрак етишмовчилиги, натрийуретик пептид, глюкоза, холестерин.

ОЦЕНКА ДИСФУНКЦИИ ПЕЧЕНИ ПРИ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ**Махмудова М.Р., Баратова М.С.**

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино, г. Бухара, Узбекистан

Резюме. Исследование артериальной гипертензии (АГ) и ишемической болезни сердца (ИБС) проводилось у 139 больных по клиническим данным. Были проанализированы параметры сердечно-сосудистой системы и биомаркеры крови. По данным ВОЗ, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания ежегодно приводят к 17,5 миллионам смертей, что составляет треть всех смертей в мире. Распространенность гипертонии среди взрослых колеблется от 30% до 45%. АГ и ИБС присутствуют у 50% и более чем у 34% пациентов, способствуя развитию микро- и макрососудистых заболеваний. Данные показывают, что у пациентов с сахарным диабетом и артериальной гипертензией риск сердечно-сосудистых осложнений в четыре раза выше.

Ключевые слова: артериальная гипертензия, ИБС, сердечная недостаточность, натрийуретический пептид, глюкоза, холестерин.

e-mail: baratova.mexriban@bsmi.uz

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), cardiovascular diseases (CVD) account for 17.5 million deaths globally each year, representing one-third of all deaths. Research has established that patients with glycemia levels of 6.1–7.0 mmol/L and 5.6–6.1 mmol/L have a 30% higher risk of developing coronary heart disease (CHD) [9]. A fasting glucose threshold of 5.6–6.9 mmol/L is classified by the American Diabetes Association (ADA) — from 2003 to the present — as impaired fasting glucose, a prediabetic state, which differs from WHO recommendations [10, 11]. According to study data, the prevalence of arterial hypertension (AH) among the adult population ranges from 30% to 45%. AH is present in more than 50% of patients and contributes to the development of micro- and macrovascular diseases [5]. There is evidence that patients with both diabetes mellitus (DM) and AH have a fourfold higher risk of developing cardiovascular diseases.

Cardiac arrhythmias occupy a leading position among the diverse pathological conditions of the cardiovascular system characterized by impaired excitability and conductivity of the atrial and ventricular myocardium [3, 6, 17], with paroxysmal arrhythmias being the most prevalent. Hemodynamic disturbances and thromboembolic complications caused by paroxysmal rhythm disorders lead to a significant increase in morbidity, mortality, and financial costs [14]. According to various authors [2, 5-10, 23], the prevalence of this pathology doubles with each decade of life — ranging from 0.5% at ages 50–59 to 9% in those aged 80–89 — and is 1.5 times higher in men than in women [14].

Despite the fact that a wide range of laboratory and instrumental methods are currently used for this purpose, the issue remains unresolved. This underscores the need to search for new non-invasive tests to identify cardiac involvement in liver dysfunction. In recent years, the determination of plasma natriuretic peptide (NP) levels has been increasingly utilized for the diagnosis of myocardial dysfunction and for prognostic purposes [1, 31].

O.A. Kislyak et al. noted a specific feature of the course of AH in young individuals, characterized by an unfavorable trend toward the early formation of target organ damage [4, 11-13, 15, 16, 23]. According to I.V. Leontyeva, young men with AH exhibit early and frequent involvement of target organs — such as the brain, heart, and peripheral vessels — in the pathological process, which determines the development of complications and an unfavorable prognosis of the disease. In recent years, an increasing mortality rate has been observed among men aged 20–35 from complications of AH and CHD [2, 3, 14, 15-19].

Currently, data are accumulating that natriuretic peptides (NPs), alongside their endocrine functions, exert important para- and autocrine effects on the heart and coronary circulation: they regulate myocardial growth, inhibit fibroblast proliferation and cardiomyocyte hypertrophy [25-29], as well as the proliferation and contractility of vascular smooth muscle cells. Furthermore, they possess cytoprotective and anti-ischemic effects and influence the endothelium of the coronary vessels [19]. Under normal conditions, the mean level of B-type NP for individuals aged 40 is 4.0–4.8 pg/mL; for men aged 85, it is 22.8–24.2 pg/mL, and for women, 18.4–26.6 pg/mL [2, 5, 10].

It has been proven that even a slight increase in these peptides in individuals without overt cardiac pathology is associated with a risk of chronic heart failure (CHF) and death [6].

The emergence of new high-tech modalities, such as computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and electroanatomical mapping, has not only enhanced the efficiency of clinical diagnostics but also expanded the possibilities for in vivo morphological research [7, 24]. Detailed morphological data on the anatomical structure of the cardiac atria enable an increase in the potential and precision of arrhythmological interventions [20-22]. At the same time, the question of the left atrial structure remains insufficiently studied to date [30, 32].

Thus, the aforementioned glycemic range and fluctuations in NT-proBNP levels are being extensively studied across various forms of heart failure; furthermore, the evaluation of liver biochemical markers is of significant interest in young patients with cardiovascular diseases and preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) presenting with paroxysmal tachycardias and atrial fibrillation.

Research Aim: To investigate and evaluate the glycemic range and NT-proBNP levels in young adults with cardiovascular diseases presenting with paroxysmal cardiac rhythm disorders.

Materials and Methods: A total of 139 men were examined, including a control group of 33 patients (mean age: 41.3 ± 2.1 years). The comparison group consisted of 106 patients (mean age: 39.1 ± 5.8 years). Both primary groups of patients were divided into 4 subgroups:

The participants were distributed as follows: Group 1 (Control Group) – 33 individuals; Group 2 (Arterial Hypertension - AH) – 41 individuals; Group 3 (Ischemic Heart Disease - IHD) – 31 individuals; and Group 4 (AH and IHD) – 34 individuals. The control group consisted of 33 age-matched men who underwent examination at the polyclinic and were recognized as somatically healthy.

Exclusion Criteria: patients aged older than 65 or younger than 30 years; acute infectious and inflammatory processes and/or chronic inflammatory processes in the exacerbation stage; unstable angina; myocardial infarction (less than 1 year prior to the study); history of cardiac surgery; valvular heart diseases; acute cerebrovascular accident (stroke); exacerbations of bronchopulmonary or gastrointestinal diseases; endocrine pathology; renal diseases with impaired function (development of signs of renal failure); liver diseases with impaired function (development of signs of hepatic failure); autoimmune diseases and collagenoses; malignancies; history of surgical intervention within the past 6 months; and psychiatric disorders.

Electrocardiography (ECG): A resting 12-lead ECG was performed on the first day of hospitalization and subsequently monitored in dynamics as clinically indicated. For recording the electrocardiograms, "ECG-300 G Biocare" (Germany) and "CARDIMAX" electrocardiographs were utilized. The analysis of the obtained results was conducted according to generally accepted methodologies.

Holter ECG Monitoring: 24-hour ambulatory ECG monitoring was performed using the "Ambulatory Electrocardiographic System," model Poly-Spectrum-SM (Holter) (Russia). The monitoring duration was 24 hours. The daily ECG recordings were analyzed for ST-T abnormalities (T-wave and ST-segment changes), as well as cardiac rhythm and conduction disturbances (mean heart rate above or below the age-appropriate norm, paroxysmal tachycardia, ventricular premature beats, supraventricular premature beats, and sick sinus syndrome). **Echocardiography (EchoCG):** Transthoracic ultrasound examination of the heart was performed using the "DC-N6 Mindray Diagnostic Ultrasound System" (China) and the "SonoScape" scanner (China), equipped with an electronic sector transducer at a frequency of 3.0 MHz. The study was conducted in one-dimensional (M-mode) and two-dimensional (B-mode) modes, as well as in Doppler echocardiography mode (utilizing pulsed-wave and continuous-wave spectral Doppler, alongside color and tissue Doppler blood flow mapping). **Determination of NT-proBNP Levels:** The determination of B-type natriuretic peptide levels in serum samples was performed using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with commercial "NT-proBNP" test systems. This ELISA test is designed for the quantitative determination of NT-proBNP in human serum samples. Additionally, an immunofluorescence method was employed using the "Finicare FIA Meter Plus" fluorescence immunoassay analyzer by Rayseen Da, in conjunction with a dry reagent system and quantitative test strips.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical data processing was performed using the STATISTICA 12.0 software package (StatSoft, Inc., USA). The critical level of statistical significance was set at 5% ($p = 0.05$).

Results and Discussion. In Group 3, the indicators were statistically significantly higher than in the comparison group patients; whereas the levels of systolic blood pressure (BP) and diastolic BP were statistically significantly lower than those in patients of Group 1. Based on the evaluation of complaints from the patients included in the study, the following data were obtained. In Group 3 patients, complaints were observed as follows: fatigue was reported by 20 patients (45%), dyspnea by 13 patients (30%), palpitations and cardiac interruptions by 24 patients (55%), cough by 7 patients (15%), weight gain by 5 patients (3%), edema of the lower extremities (lower legs, feet) by 36 patients (9%), and discomfort in the heart area by 13 (28%) patients.

Fatigue was observed in 11 patients (25%) of Group 2; dyspnea was reported by 36 patients (8%); palpitations and cardiac interruptions were absent; cough was absent; nocturnal paroxysms of suffocation and weight gain were observed in 7 patients (7%); edema of the lower extremities (lower legs, feet) was present in 7 patients (6%); and pain in the heart area was reported by 7 patients (10%).

At the initial stage of data processing, NT-proBNP levels were compared. In Group 3 patients, the mean NT-proBNP level was 385.3 pg/mL, which was statistically significantly higher than in the control group, where the NT-proBNP level was 103.3 pg/mL, and statistically significantly higher than in Group 1 patients (204.6 pg/mL). The indicators of "high-normal glycemia" and "normoglycemia" occupied an intermediate position — these individuals were significantly older than the representatives of Group 3, but significantly younger than the patients in Groups 1-2 (Table 1).

Table 1

Study Parameters	Group 1 (n = 41): AH	Group 2 (n = 31): CHD	Group 3 (n = 34): Liver Dysfunction, AH + CHD	Control Group (n = 33)
Male gender, n (%)	49/34,8	48,7/39,7	27/50	25/45
Fasting blood glucose, mmol/L	5,8 (5,7; 5,9)	4,7 (4,3; 5,1)	5,45 (6,2; 6,7)	4,2 (4,1; 5,0)
Age, years	40 (34; 46)	41,8 (34; 49,5)	42,3 (36; 48,5)	41,8 (34; 49,5)
Body weight, kg	83 (70; 92)	72 (62; 72)	86* (78; 98)	69 (63; 75)
BMI, kg/m ²	27,3 (25; 30)	26 (24; 28)	29 * (28; 31)	22 (20; 23)
Total cholesterol, mmol/L	5,4 (4,75; 6,2)	4,8 (4,2; 5,6)	5,5 (4,5; 6,3)	4,8 (4,2; 5,6)
NT-proBNP, pg/mL	204,5 (206,1;244,4)	315,2 * (238,3;247,3)	385,8 ** (336,3;398,4)	103,9 (98,9;108,3)

Note: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.05$ — significance of differences between groups.

In Group 1 patients, the NT-proBNP level was 204.9 pg/mL, which was statistically significantly higher than in the control group (103.9 pg/mL). In Group 3 patients, the NT-proBNP level reached 385.9 pg/mL, which was statistically higher compared to the control group (103.9 pg/mL) (Table 2).

Table 2

Parameters	Control Group (n = 33)	Group with AH (n = 41)	Group with CHD (n = 31)	Group with Liver Dysfunction and AH+CHD (n = 34)
IVST (mm)	9,574±1,12	11,07±1,224	9,37±1,124	13,24±3,013
LVPWT (mm)	8,348±2,22	10,048±2,330	10,348±2,330	12,029±2,785
LA Volume (ml)	31,320±2,18	43,43±12,21	40,43±13,21	45,43±12,11
LVEF (%)	64,16±5,10	57,256±5,172	55,256±5,372	55,468±5,282
LVM (B-mode), g	175,136±4,41	211,21±123,56	227,115±105,12	249,12±105,12**
LVMI (g/m ²)	98,297±9,09	206.24±7,12	238,125±7,61	336,125±7,51**

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.05 — significance of differences between groups.

Thus, the lowest concentration of natriuretic peptides (NP) in the blood was observed in Group 1; meanwhile, a statistically significant increase in NT-proBNP levels was identified in Groups 2 and 3 compared to the group of somatically healthy individuals. However, Group 3 patients exhibited a statistically significantly more pronounced increase in NT-proBNP levels than those in Groups 1 and 2. This reflects a more significant impact on the left atrium with the stretching of its walls and indicates the possibility of utilizing this indicator in clinical practice as an important diagnostic criterion for the development of heart failure.

Our study revealed that in patients with liver dysfunction in Groups 1 and 2, glucose and cholesterol levels remained within the normal range. However, in Group 3, these indicators were substantially higher and statistically significant; furthermore, NT-proBNP levels exceeded those of the control group. A direct correlation was discovered between liver dysfunction and NT-proBNP levels in these patient groups. This reflects the presence of excessive stretching of the ventricles and the left atrium, indicating structural and hemodynamic remodeling in these patients. At the same time, statistically significantly higher levels of cholesterol, glucose, and NT-proBNP in Groups 2 and 3 point to a greater severity of cardiovascular remodeling processes and liver dysfunction.

Conclusions: In Group 1 patients with AH, liver dysfunction occurs in 41.5% of cases, while in Group 2 patients, liver dysfunction was observed in 31.5%. In patients with elevated systolic blood pressure, disturbances in the daily BP profile, and increased pulse pressure, an elevation in liver enzyme levels was observed, indicating liver dysfunction. In patients of Groups 2 and 3, the elevation of NT-proBNP levels and liver dysfunction may serve as markers for the modification of the disease course, accompanied by the structural remodeling of the cardiovascular system. Furthermore, it can be asserted that the presence of paroxysmal tachycardia and atrial fibrillation, which occurred more frequently in Group 3 patients, acts as an additional factor contributing to left atrial remodeling.

Summary: Liver dysfunction and natriuretic peptides (NP) are valuable biomarkers widely used in clinical practice for the diagnosis and prognosis of the course and development of heart failure.

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